

Ion-Solvent Interactions in DMSO + Water + KBr System at 308.15 K

A ALI*, A K NAIN and S. AHMED

Department of Chemistry, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi-110 025

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Recently, much interest has been shown to the study of ternary solutions containing electrolytes^{1,2}. The details of the nature and mechanism of the interactions in DMSO + water mixed with an electrolyte have received relatively little attention. Moreover, to the best of our knowledge, no ultrasonic study of this system has been reported earlier. DMSO belongs to the so-called 'supersolvent' having a wide range of applicability in chemical and biological reactions^{3,4}. Due to the absence of a proton-donor group (and also the value of Kirkwood factor $g \approx 1$), DMSO does not self-associate through hydrogen bonding^{4,5}, whereas the unique structure of water in which both the three-dimensional character and the presence of hydrogen bonds make these two solvents behave differently. Some investigators⁶ treated the binary mixture of liquids as an 'averaged pure solvent' model which could not explain the possible preferential solvation of cations/anions by either component of the solvent mixture. Free volume is considered as an important fundamental factor in explaining the variation in the physicochemical properties of liquids and solutions, whereas the energy-volume coefficient $(\partial E/\partial V)_T$, called internal pressure, is the resultant of the forces of attraction and repulsion between the entities present in the solution. Therefore, V_f and P_i will reflect changes in the structure and inter-component interactions present in the system. These considerations led us to undertake the present investigation.

Results and Discussion

The experimental values of density and viscosity and of ultrasonic velocity in the solutions of KBr in DMSO + water mixtures, measured at 308.15 K together with free

volume and internal pressure, are listed in Table 1. Using the measured values of density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity, the values of free volume and internal pressure were evaluated with the help of the standard relations⁷,

$$V_f = (Mu/K\eta)^{3/2} \quad (1)$$

$$P_i = bRT (K\eta/ u)^{1/2} \rho^{2/3} / M^{7/6} \quad (2)$$

where, M is the effective molecular weight of the mixture, K is a constant ($=4.28 \times 10^9$), b is the packing factor in liquids equal to 1.78 for close-packed hexagonal structure⁸, R the gas constant, T the temperature (K). The variation of V_f and P_i of KBr in DMSO + H₂O mixtures at 308.15 K are shown in Fig. 1. In the absence of solute KBr, DMSO associates with water through hydrogen bonding⁹. Formation

Fig 1 Variation of free volume (V_f) and internal pressure (P_i) with concentration of KBr in (o) 20% and (•) 45% (DMSO by vol) DMSO + water mixtures at 308.15 K.

TABLE I—DENSITY (ρ , 10^3 kg m^{-3}), VISCOSITY (η , $10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$), ULTRASONIC VELOCITY (u , m s^{-1}), FREE VOLUME (V_f , 10^{-8} m^3) AND INTERNAL PRESSURE (P_i , 10^9 N m^{-2}) OF KBr SOLUTIONS IN DMSO + WATER (20 AND 45% DMSO BY VOL) MIXTURES AT 308.15 K

[KBr] mol dm ⁻³	20% DMSO					45% DMSO				
	ρ	η	u	V_f	P_i	ρ	η	u	V_f	P_i
0.00	1.0186	1.1169	1602.7	1.9431	2.2159	1.0580	2.1210	1684.5	1.1890	2.2273
0.10	1.0266	1.1061	1603.8	2.0022	2.1913	1.0658	2.0490	1679.0	1.2752	2.1812
0.25	1.0391	1.1129	1605.4	2.0297	2.1782	1.0770	2.0460	1677.7	1.3018	2.1625
0.50	1.0603	1.1113	1606.1	2.1084	2.1460	1.0859	2.0288	1675.5	1.3587	2.1262
0.75	1.0813	1.1155	1608.7	2.1758	2.1187	1.1153	1.9597	1673.2	1.4742	2.0463
1.00	1.1029	1.1173	1609.5	2.2470	2.0921	1.1346	1.9697	1673.0	1.5128	2.0275
Average error				± 0.0065	± 0.0033				± 0.0191	± 0.0117

of associated species of the type $\text{DMSO} : 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has also been suggested by Ritzoulis⁴. Such associated species are expected due to stronger DMSO-water hydrogen bonding than water-water hydrogen bonding⁹. Since both the liquids, water and DMSO, have high dielectric constants (48.9 at 293.15 K and 78.5 at 298.15 K)¹⁰ respectively, their mixtures are expected to be good solvents for the ionisation of KBr. The V_f is found to increase (Fig. 1) with the concentration of KBr in both the solvent mixtures. Univalent ions like K^+ and Br^- are strong structure-breakers¹¹, and break the solvent structure with subsequent increase in V_f . The increase in V_f is also favoured by the depolarising effect of Br^- ions¹². On the other hand, at all concentrations of KBr studied, a pronounced decrease in V_f is observed as the concentration of DMSO in the mixture increases (45% DMSO), suggesting a certain tendency of preferential solvation of K^+ ion by DMSO and probably Br^- ion by water molecules. In fact, the formation of relatively long-lived K^+ -DMSO complexes (but not with water) has been suggested¹⁰ on the basis of nmr study of ion-solvent interactions. This is in agreement with the results reported by Cox *et al.*¹³, using free energy of transfer of electrolyte (MX, an alkali metal halide) from water to DMSO, that the cation interacts more favourably with DMSO than with water. Very recently¹⁴, a study of the density profiles of O, S and CH_3 sites of DMSO around the Cl^- ion suggests that there is little solvation of Cl^- ion by DMSO molecules. In the light of this fact, the solvation of Br^- ion by DMSO would be expected to be decreased further due to its larger size. In fact, anionic solvation data point to stronger interactions of Br^- ion with protic solvents such as water, than with dipolar aprotic solvents such as DMSO¹⁵. Based on the aforementioned discussions, we are able to summarise the various interactions involved in the system under study : (i) as mentioned earlier⁹, the interaction of the type $\text{DMSO} : \text{H}_2\text{O}$ being stronger than water-water interaction tends to decrease the value of V_f of the DMSO + water solvent mixtures, (ii) strong structure-breaking ability of K^+ and Br^- ions and also the depolarising effect of Br^- ions lead to an increase in V_f and (iii) preferential solvation of K^+ and Br^- ions by DMSO and water molecules respectively, decreases the value of V_f . The present results can be interpreted in the light of these effects. Although, the effects (i) and (iii) are significant, the effect (ii) seems to be dominant favouring overall increase in the V_f as the concentration of KBr increases in both the solvent mixtures. Such type of behaviour in V_f is also reported for $\text{NaCl} + N,N$ -dimethylformamide + water ternary system¹² at 0.75 *m* NaCl.

A perusal of Fig. 1 indicates that internal pressure

(hence, the cohesive energy of the system which is a measure of internal pressure) decreases with increase in concentration of KBr in both the solvent mixtures. It is interesting to note that the trends in the variation of V_f and P_i with concentration of solute are opposite to each other. Similar trends in the variation of V_f and P_i have been reported² for $\text{MgSO}_4 + \text{dioxane} + \text{water}$ mixtures. This decrease in P_i with concentration of solute further supports the view that structure-breaking effect of K^+ and Br^- ions is the deciding factor in the $\text{KBr} + \text{DMSO} + \text{water}$ ternary system. An increase in P_i at all concentrations of solute on going from 20 to 45% DMSO may be attributed to the increased solvation of ions, mainly of K^+ by DMSO, at higher DMSO composition.

Suryanarayana¹⁶ showed that the entropy of a condensed phase is related to the internal pressure as

$$S_T = S_0 - 3 R \ln P_i \quad (3)$$

where, S_T and S_0 are the entropies at temperature T , and when the $P_i = 1$ respectively. Thus, order of a system is directly related to its internal pressure. As the value of P_i of the system under study decreases with increase in concentration of KBr (Fig. 1) in both the solvent mixtures, then according to equation (3), there would be an increase in the entropy, thereby, producing greater disorder in the system; which is expected due to predominantly structure-breaking effect of K^+ and Br^- ions. But, P_i increases at all concentrations of KBr studied as we move from 20 to 45% DMSO + water mixture (Fig. 1) making the system more ordered owing to decrease in the entropy. This reinforces our earlier view that at higher DMSO concentration in the DMSO + water mixture, relatively stronger K^+ -DMSO complexes are formed and the strength of the complex formed increases as the concentration of KBr increases in the mixture.

Experimental

DMSO (Merck) was purified further¹⁷. Demineralised water was double-distilled for preparing the DMSO + H_2O (20 and 45% DMSO by volume) mixtures. KBr (Merck) was recrystallised from acetone-water (1 : 1, v/v) and dried under reduced pressure at 373.15 K. Density was measured with a single-stem calibrated pycnometer of bulb capacity $8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3$, the accuracy being ± 0.0002 . Viscosity was determined using a Cannon-Ubbelohde viscometer with a reproducibility of $\pm 0.005 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The ultrasonic measurement was made using a single crystal interferometer at 3 MHz with an accuracy of $\pm 0.04\%$. All the measurements were made in a water thermostat maintained at $308.15 \pm 0.05 \text{ K}$.

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